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Title: EFFECT OF SOLVENT STRUCTURE AND AMINE ADDITION ON THE
DEPOLYMERIZATION OF A BITUMINOUS VENEZUELAN COAL

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Manuel Martínez Santana, Ph.D.

Corresponding Author's Institution: Instituto de Ciencias de la Tierra

First Author: Adriana C Gamboa, PhD

Order of Authors: Adriana C Gamboa, PhD; Manuel Martínez Santana, Ph.D.;
Grony Garbán, PhD.; Ivan Esteves, MSc; Marcos E Escobar , PhD; Karla
Quintero, PhD; Erica Lorenzo , PhD

Abstract: This article describes the solvent identity, composition and structure effects on the depolymerization/extraction yield of a bituminous coal from the Naricual coalfield, Eastern Venezuela. We employed benzene, chloroform, N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF), 3-methylphenol (m-cresol), hexahydropyridine (piperidine) and toluene as solvents; and dimethylamine and p-phenylenediamine as additive (coal: amine 10:1 ratio), for testing possible changes in yield in a Soxhlet extraction system during 12 hours. The extraction/depolymerization capabilities were increased as follow: benzene < toluene < chloroform < DMF < m-cresol < piperidine. Boiling temperature, Hildebrand solubility and empirical polarity parameter ET(30) are not adequate for explaining the yield behavior of the solvents used in Naricual coal extraction. On the other hand, H-bonding ability and electron-donor availability in the solvent are determinant factors in the coal extraction/depolymerization process. The results confirm the important role of specific interactions in determining the extraction/depolymerization behavior of this coal. When amines were added the yields increase significantly, but in a different extent. Amines added opens the coal structure for solvent penetration. Identity of the amine and the pair solvent/amine synergy are determinants in the depolymerization of the studied coal.

Suggested Reviewers: Burnham K Burnham PhD
Consultant and Consulting Professor, Department of Energy Resources
Engineering, Stanford University
aburnham@stanford.edu

He recently published a book with a chapter dedicated to "Structures of Coal, Kerogen, and Asphaltenes" with discussion about the relative importance of various forces holding coal clusters together

Opaprasit Pakorn PhD
Assoc. Professor, Sirindhorn International Institute of Technology
(SIIT), Thammasat University, Thailand
pakorn@siit.tu.ac.th

His Doctoral Thesis was related with the coal structure and the interaction with solvents

Gonzalo Marquez PhD

Titular professor, Departamento de Ingeniería Minera, Mecánica y Energética, , Universidad de Huelva, Spain
gonzalo.marquez@diq.uhu.es

He worked with Venezuelan coals as a geochemist.

Ricardo Angulo

Professor, Grupo de investigación del carbón GIC, Departamento de Química e Ingeniería Quím, Universidad del Atlántico, Barranquilla, Colombia

ricardoangulo20@hotmail.com

He worked with colombian coals, related with solvent effects and liquefaction

Sönmez Özgür PhD

Professor , Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Arts and Science, Mersin University, Ciftlikkoy Campus, Mersin, Turkey

osonmez@mersin.edu.tr

He is active working in solvent extraction of coals and related materials

1 Highlights

2 Yield depolymerization of Naricual coal reach 50% with piperidine

3 Contribution of the 4-PhDA to the coal depolymerization increased yield
4 until 73%

5 H-bonding and Lewis acid-base interactions responsible for coal solvolysis

6

7 1. Introduction

8 In carbochemistry, the coal-derived liquid can be used as precursor for tar,
9 oils, solvents, rubbers, pigments, asphalts, and many other useful
10 products[1]. Several procedures were assayed in obtaining liquids from coal:
11 hydrogenation, pyrolysis, liquefaction, controlled oxidation, dry-
12 distillation, solvent-refined coal. Solvent extraction technology has been
13 practiced in the production of clean (low-ash, low-sulfur) coal[2]. During
14 solvolysis, the solvent breaks the intermolecular forces between coal
15 molecules, such as H-bonding, van der Waal's and London forces, p-p
16 interactions, and makes its own bonding with coal molecules; this process
17 is, in fact, a depolymerization[3,4]. Depolymerization is the initial path
18 in the coal liquefaction[5,6], a treatment that allows to obtain low
19 molecular-weight products.

20 Bituminous and subbituminous coals exhibit low extraction yield (< 3%) with
21 conventional solvents as chloroform or dichloromethane. On the other hand,

22 several authors have reported higher yields with more aggressive solvents
23 (e.g. pyridine, tetrahydrofuran -THF-, ethylenediamine) [7,8]. Mix of
24 solvents, pre-demineralization with acids, previous thermal treatment and
25 other added products were also tested [9-13]; in general, solvolysis of coal
26 increases with time and temperature [14]. Presence of low quantities of
27 specific compounds as well affects the depolymerization extent. Certain
28 aromatic amines added in low proportion in the mixture coal-solvent rise
29 the extraction procedure, reporting increases from 51,4 to 81,3 % [15].

30 Venezuela has large coal reserves, most of these located in the western
31 region of the country. These coals cover a wide range of chemical and
32 petrographic characteristics [16,17]. The coals are mainly of low rank due
33 to their Tertiary age. At the eastern of the country, Naricual coals are
34 high-bituminous in rank, with potential reserves estimated in 100 MMTM [18].
35 Only few studies have carried out on these coals [19,20] achieving in some
36 cases satisfactory results in terms of the increase in extraction yields
37 that resulted from mild to moderate. This article examines the use of
38 organic solvents with different extractive efficiency and their
39 relationships with some empirical parameters derived from solvents, as well
40 as the use of amines on the extraction/depolymerization yields in
41 bituminous Naricual coal.

42 2. Experimental procedure

43 2.1. Sample description

44 A Finely crushed Naricual Composite Coal Sample (NCCS) was prepared
45 (obtained from a mixing of five coal seams: Aragüita, Mallorquín,
46 Capiricual, Orégano River and Santa María) of the Naricual coal mines,
47 currently abandoned. The results of the proximate analyses are summarized
48 in Table 1.

49 2.2. Solvents description

50 Six solvents were examined: benzene, trichloromethane (chloroform), N,N-
51 dimethylformamide (DMF), 3-methyl-phenol (m-cresol), hexahydropyridine
52 (piperidine) and methylbenzene (toluene). The general properties, electron
53 donor- acceptor properties, and solubility parameters of the solvents were
54 obtained from the literature and summarized in Table 2. Some solubility
55 parameters from coal tar pitch "as solvent" from Weinberg and Fen[21]
56 were included in the table for comparative purposes.

57 A clean coal sample was crushed and passed through 60 mesh (-250 μm) size
58 sieve. Freshly distilled solvents were used (benzene, toluene, chloroform);
59 and DMF, m-cresol and piperidine were used without further purification
60 because they had reagent grade (Aldrich). Solvent extractions of the
61 crushed coal samples (2 g of crushed coal sample weighted at 0.0001 g) were
62 carried out using standard Soxhlet extraction assemblies at the atmospheric
63 reflux temperatures of the solvents employed. The ratio of solvent to coal
64 was maintained near 100:1 v/w); the extraction times were approximately 12
65 h. The same procedure was repeated for each sample with the addition of
66 dimethylamine (DMA) and 4-phenylenediamine (4-PhDA) without further

67 purification (10:1 w/w coal: amine). The extraction and removal of the
68 solvent were performed in the same stainless-steel ultracentrifuge tube.
69 After extraction, the solvent was recovered by reduced pressure
70 distillation.

71 3. Results

72 The yield (calculated on dry and ash-free basis -d.a.f.-) for coal and the
73 coal/amine extractions (Table 3) are lesser than 4 % in benzene, toluene
74 and chloroform. It is evident that these solvents only remove occluded or
75 weakly bounded organic molecules inside the coal matrix.

76 Benzene, chloroform and toluene behaved like conventional solvents when
77 they reacted with Naricual coal: low yields, an extracted material similar
78 in consistency with a brown semi-solid wax, and strong smell of oil. These
79 solvents were classified by Dryden coal-solvent scale[26] as class I, and
80 only will solubilize low-molecular weight organic compounds occluded in the
81 macromolecular coal matrix.

82 3.1. Influence of the boiling point of the solvent

83 It has been established that the higher the boiling temperature of the
84 solvent, the higher the extraction yield[26]. For the solvents assayed in
85 this work, there is no correlation between the extraction yield and the
86 boiling point. Yield with toluene (0.1%) has no comparison with the yield
87 with piperidine as solvent (51% w/w), although both solvents have very

88 similar boiling points. Solvents as DMF or m-cresol, with boiling points
89 higher than piperidine, had lower power extractive.

90 **3.2. Hildebrand solubility parameters**

91 The Hildebrand solubility parameter of a solvent represents its solubility
92 as a function of molecular cohesion. This parameter (Table 2) was
93 correlated with extraction yield (Table 3) for Naricual coal (Fig. 1).
94 However, a clear relationship between the parameter of solvent and
95 extraction yield could not be found. Visibly, solvents with high extractive
96 power don' t match in any trend.

97 **3.3. Influence of solvent polarity**

98 The empirical solvent polarity parameter, ET(30), proposed first by Dimroth
99 and Reichardt in 1963[23] is a measure of the level or degree of polarity
100 in the solvent; very low values in benzene and toluene (Table 2) are in
101 agreement with their nonpolar features. These solvents exhibit low yields
102 (Table 3). However, there is a discrepancy with the other solvents: the
103 higher yield was obtained with piperidine, whose ET(30) value is lower than
104 for chloroform, with a very low extraction yield (Fig. 2).

105 A good positive correlation ($R^2=0.953$, excluding piperidine) between ET (30)
106 values of solvents and the extraction yield of Naricual coal is shown in
107 Fig. 2. The trend observed seems to suggest an influence of the polarity on
108 the extraction power of the used solvents. However, for piperidine, it is
109 obvious that other explanation must be considered.

110 3.4. Influence of solvent Lewis acid-base affinity

111 The very low donor number (DN) and the negative value for the difference
112 between the donor number (DN) minus acceptor number (AN) values[24] in the
113 solvents classified as class I by Dryden (benzene, chloroform, toluene)
114 implies a negligible ability for acid-base interactions. On the other hand,
115 for DMF, m-cresol and piperidine, the extraction yields were significant
116 higher, with clear correlation with the Dryden class (III for DMF, IV for
117 m-cresol and V for piperidine), the DN and DN-AN value (Table 2). This
118 result provides information about the nature of the driven forces of the
119 solvolysis process. In that case, we prefer to use the term
120 depolymerization instead extraction, because is demonstrated that not only
121 occluded molecules are removed. A real disintegration takes place in the
122 coal organic matrix, where the solvent acts as a Lewis base, and active
123 points of coal react as Lewis acid^{22-23,26-27}; other interactions may be
124 present too, e.g. chemical reactions[29] or ion-exchange[30].

125 Figure 3 shows the effect of the acid-base behavior of assayed solvents
126 (expressed as the DN) on the yield of extraction in Naricual coal. As far
127 we know, no literature data is available on the Gutmann's donor number of
128 m-cresol. The higher the donor number, the stronger the interaction between
129 the solvent (as a base) and coal (as an acid), with the increasing yield of
130 coal depolymerization. In this graph, piperidine appears in the main
131 positive trend; the extracting power of this solvent is directly related

132 with the donor - acceptor interactions with the macromolecular matrix of
133 coal.

134 3.5. Hansen parameters

135 After Hansen, there are three major types of interactions in common organic
136 materials[25]: The most general are the nonpolar interactions, that also
137 been called dispersion interactions, δD . The second one are the permanent
138 dipole-permanent dipole interactions that cause a polar cohesive energy,
139 δP . The third major cohesive energy source is hydrogen bonding, δH , an
140 electron exchange parameter. These three parameters (Hansen Solubility
141 Parameters HSP; Table 2) can be represented in a 3-dimensional diagram,
142 generating a sphere or ellipsoid. For instance, spheres from solvents
143 assayed in this work appear plotted in Figure 4. Coal tar pitch and
144 asphaltenes are also showed, as an approximate of coal structure.

145 Figure 4 is a plot derived for solvents and soluble materials. Because of
146 that, coals cannot be represented. However, some materials can give a
147 picture of the probable position of coal if could be represented (coal tar
148 pitch). The most distinctive Hansen parameter towards coal-like structures
149 (coal tar pitch) is, in fact, the H-bonding. Vicinity of toluene, benzene
150 and chloroform pseudospheres to the asphaltene ellipsoid explain its
151 goodness as solvent for this material. Nevertheless, assuming that coal
152 structure is more similar to its derived product, coal tar pitch, these
153 solvents are far away of the "sphere" of coal tar. As this plot suggest,
154 best solvents for coal are those near to coal tar, with higher H-bonding

155 ability. It is not surprising that m-cresol and piperidine are good
156 extractive solvents for coal.

157 3.6. Influence of the added amine

158 In all cases, assayed amines in the solvolysis interaction with Naricual
159 coal increase the extraction/depolymerization yield, although in different
160 extent (Table 2). For class I solvents, the increase in yield exceeded 100%.
161 As the solvent has greater extractive power, the effect of the addition of
162 the amine decreases; however, in mass, the effect is important (Fig. 5).

163 Differences in the effect of each amine assayed are very notorious. The
164 incremental effect in yield for DMA is moderate, in comparison with 4-PhDA.
165 However, the extent of this increasing yield varies with the solvent. There
166 are differences between the three class I solvents. With benzene and
167 toluene, the yield increases nearly twice; with chloroform, the yield
168 increases 9 times. For DMF, chloroform and piperidine, the effect of this
169 amine in the extraction was higher than for m-cresol, toluene and benzene
170 (Fig. 5). The reasons why amines are so effective and why its effectiveness
171 is dependent on the coal and/or solvent used still is not clear[31].

172 4. Discussion

173 As expected, the extraction yield obtained using hydrocarbons (benzene,
174 toluene) is lower than that of other employed solvents, indicating a poorer
175 extractability. The N atom in piperidine has one lone pair electron
176 available for hydrogen bonding with coal OH groups. Even though the N atom

177 in DMF also contains a lone pair electron, its electron donor ability is
178 lowered by resonance stabilization with the adjacent carbonyl group.
179 Moreover, the N atom in DMF is methyl substituted and this gives some
180 steric hindrance.

181 The boiling temperature, Hildebrand solubility, or the empirical polarity
182 parameter ET (30) are not adequate for explaining the yield behavior of the
183 solvents used in Naricual coal. Gutmann's parameter DN allows to explain
184 the trend observed, suggesting a strong influence of Lewis acid-base
185 interactions. Piperidine behavior is satisfactorily explained with this
186 parameter (Fig. 3). However, a better correlation ($R^2=0.994$) between
187 solvent parameters and the extraction yield is obtained with DN/AN
188 parameter, instead of DN or DN-AN[32] (Fig. 6).

189 The yield enhancement by amine presence during the
190 extraction/depolymerization process is strongly related with the
191 accessibility of the solvents to the potentially extractable but originally
192 entrapped extractable components of coal in the coal matrix. In all
193 solvents, amines promote an enhancement in extraction/depolymerization.
194 However, for dimethylamine (DMA), the effect is lower than 4-
195 phenylenediamine (4-PhDA). Role of amines in the depolymerization is not
196 clear. Various functions of amines in coal extraction/depolymerization have
197 been hypothesized so far, including cleavage reactions of carbon-oxygen
198 bonds by amine, and physical effects such as swelling/solubility
199 enhancement and breaking of non-covalent bonds. For Naricual coal, the

200 effect of the amine depends of the nature of the amine and the solvent. 4-
201 PhDA is more efficient than DMA as additive in the depolymerization process
202 assisted by solvents, and can be explained by a greater ability to break
203 the associations among coal molecules through the interaction of the amines
204 with coal, via hydrogen bonds[15]. 4-PhDA opens the coal structure for
205 solvent penetration, and then the boiling solvent disrupts more the non-
206 covalent interactions, which hold soluble material to the network.

207 5. Conclusions

208 The effects of various solvents and amines on the
209 extraction/depolymerization yield of bituminous Naricual coals were
210 investigated. The following conclusions may be drawn:

211 (1) Piperidine as solvent, combined with 4-phenylenediamine added, was
212 found to be very effective for the increase in the extraction yield until
213 73.4 % w/w.

214 (2) Boiling point and polarity of the solvent are not important factors
215 explaining the behavior and yield observed.

216 (3) Lewis acid-base interactions are the main reason for the yield
217 enhancement. A mechanism that noncovalent bonds in the macromolecular
218 matrix of coal are broken by the high-extractive solvents is proposed,
219 where H-bonding interactions are a decisive part of these depolymerization
220 process.

221 (4) Amines act increasing swelling and opening the coal structure via
222 hydrogen bonds.

223 Conflict of interest

224 None.

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314

315

Table 1. Proximate analysis of parent coal

316

Coal	PROXIMATE ANALYSIS (%)			
	Moisture	Volatile matter	Fixed carbon	Ash
Naricual A	5.51	42.8	48.39	3.3
Naricual M	3.93	40.9	50.92	4.25
Naricual C	5.16	38.21	49.85	6.78
Naricual O	7.01	32.88	47.89	12.22
Naricual S	4.39	38.28	53.49	3.84
NCCS	5.20	39.91	49.54	5.35

317

318

319

320 **Table 2.** Solvent class, polarity and solubility parameters, and electron
 321 donor-acceptor number of solvents.

<i>Solvent</i>	<i>Solvent class</i> [22]	$E_T(30)$ [23] <i>kcal/mol</i>	<i>Gutmann's parameters</i> [24]			<i>Hildebrand solubility parameter</i> [23]	<i>Hansen parameters</i> [25]		
			<i>DN</i>	<i>AN</i>	<i>DN-AN</i>		<i>Dispersion force</i>	<i>Polar force</i>	<i>Hydrogen bonding</i>
<i>Benzene</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>34.3</i>	<i>0.1</i>	<i>8.2</i>	<i>-8.1</i>	<i>18.8</i>	<i>18.4</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>2.0</i>
<i>Chloroform</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>39.1</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>23.1</i>	<i>-19.1</i>	<i>19.0</i>	<i>17.8</i>	<i>3.1</i>	<i>5.7</i>
<i>DMF</i>	<i>III</i>	<i>43.2</i>	<i>26.6</i>	<i>16.0</i>	<i>+10.6</i>	<i>24.8</i>	<i>17.4</i>	<i>13.7</i>	<i>11.3</i>
<i>m-Cresol</i>	<i>IV</i>	<i>52.4</i>	-	-	-	<i>27.2</i>	<i>18.0</i>	<i>5.1</i>	<i>12.9</i>
<i>Piperidine</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>35.5</i>	<i>51</i>	-	-	<i>8.7</i>	<i>17.6</i>	<i>4.5</i>	<i>8.9</i>
<i>Toluene</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>33.9</i>	<i>0.1</i>	<i>6.8</i>	<i>-6.7</i>	<i>18.1</i>	<i>18.0</i>	<i>1.4</i>	<i>2.0</i>
<i>Coal tar</i> [21]	-	-	-	-	-	~20-24[21]	<i>18.7</i>	<i>7.5</i>	<i>8.9</i>

322

323

324 **Table 3.** Yield extraction of Naricual coal NCCS and NCCS + amines (dry and ash
325 free, d.a.f.) for the used solvents in this work. Boiling point of solvents are
326 included.

327

<i>Solvent</i>	<i>T_b / °C</i>	<i>% yield (d. a. f.)</i>		
		<i>NCCS</i>	<i>NCCS + DMA</i>	<i>NCCS + 4-PhDA</i>
<i>Benzene</i>	<i>80</i>	<i>0.98</i>	<i>1.5</i>	<i>1.61</i>
<i>Chloroform</i>	<i>62</i>	<i>3.88</i>	<i>6.0</i>	<i>30.0</i>
<i>DMF</i>	<i>153</i>	<i>17.6</i>	<i>20.0</i>	<i>41.9</i>
<i>m-Cresol</i>	<i>202</i>	<i>43.1</i>	<i>47.3</i>	<i>49.4</i>
<i>Piperidine</i>	<i>106</i>	<i>50.2</i>	<i>52.7</i>	<i>73.4</i>
<i>Toluene</i>	<i>110</i>	<i>1.21</i>	<i>2.09</i>	<i>6.21</i>

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329

330 **Figure legends**

331

332 **Figure 1.**– Plot of extraction yield versus Hildebrand solubility parameter.

333

334 **Figure 2.**– Influence of the polarity of the solvent (expressed by the
335 empirical polarity parameter ET (30)) in the yield extraction
336 (d. a. f. basis) of Naricual coal composite sample.

337

338 **Figure 3.**– Relationship between the donocity (donor number, DN of Gutmann)
339 of the solvent and the yield extraction (d. a. f. basis) of Naricual
340 coal composite sample.

341

342 **Figure 4.**– Plot of the Hansen 3D pseudospheres for solvents used in this
343 work. Also represented the pseudospheres for coal tar and
344 asphaltene. Modified from Hansen[25].

345

346 **Figure 5.**– Influence of the solvent in the yield extraction (d. a. f. basis)
347 of Naricual coal composite sample (NCCS, left), and with addition
348 of dimethylamine (NCCS + DMA, center) and 4-phenylenediamine (NCCS
349 + 4-PhDA, right).

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351 **Figure 6.** - Plot of DN/AN relationship vs. extraction yield for Naricual
352 coals. Piperidine and m-cresol were not represented due to lack of
353 AN data.

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